

THE STRENGTH OF MECHANICALLY FASTENED
JOINTS IN 'KEVLAR' FIBRE-REINFORCED EPOXY RESIN

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Summary

This paper summarises the results from a large test programme which measured the static strength of mechanically fastened joints in 'Kevlar' fibre/epoxy laminates; single and double lap riveted joints and double shear bolted joints were investigated. Behaviour was generally found to be the same as similar joints in carbon and glass fibre/epoxy laminates, although strength levels were lower. The 'Kevlar' joints displayed a ductile failure.

Introduction

In the continuing quest for improved efficiency, particularly in the aerospace & automotive industries, designers have, in recent years, turned more and more towards high performance composite materials, i.e. thermosetting resins reinforced by glass, carbon or 'Kevlar' fibres. Following early use for non-structural parts these materials, especially carbon fibre reinforced plastics (CFRP), are now seeing applications in primary, i.e. main load bearing, structures. The use of 'Kevlar' fibre reinforced plastic (KFRP) is increasing rapidly, although mainly for secondary rather than primary structural components. Glass fibre reinforced plastic (GFRP) has, of course, been used in a wide variety of applications over several decades.

Any inaccuracies in design or manufacture of mechanical joints in metal components are alleviated by the yielding behaviour of the metal. Not only are fibre reinforced plastics (FRP) anisotropic, leading to higher stress concentrations, they are usually also brittle and would thus appear to be unsuitable candidates for mechanical fastening. Fortunately, however, judicious selection of fibre orientation, fibre type and the details of the microscopic failure mechanisms means that such materials can exhibit pseudo-plastic behaviour. Consequently, mechanical joints in composites can show adequate structural efficiency (1) and, together with ease of fabrication and inspection, cost efficiency.

The behaviour of mechanical joints in CFRP and GFRP is now well characterised and a considerable body of experimental data is available in the open literature, (2), (3), (4). In contrast, although some work has been reported for bolted joints in KFRP by van Dreumel, (5) and (6), data for this material is scarce.

Objectives

The objectives of the work reported here were to increase the data base relating to mechanically fastened joints in KFRP by carrying out static tests on riveted and bolted joints (7). Of particular interest were the joint type (single or double lap), geometric effects (width, etc) and the influence of the inherently low compressive strength of 'Kevlar' fibres.

Experimental Programme

Specimen Fabrication

Materials. All specimens were prepared from a balanced plain weave fabric of 'Kevlar' fibres preimpregnated with Ciba-Geigy 913 epoxy resin. After autoclave curing to the suppliers recommended schedule one layer, or ply, had a thickness of 0.083 mm, with a fibre volume fraction of 0.62. Clearly one layer gave a 0/90° fibre lay-up. Originally the intention was also to test specimens made from unidirectional prepreg; however, such material could not be obtained.

Laminates. Using the woven prepreg, suitably cut and oriented, laminated plates of 430 mm x 300 mm were produced. The lay-ups were either 0/90°, ± 45° or 0/90/± 45°. In the last arrangement fibre directions alternated layer-by-layer, the 0/90° always being on the outside. All lay-ups were symmetric about the mid-plane of the laminate thickness. The 0/90° laminates were fabricated in thicknesses of 1 mm (12 plies), 1.36 mm (16 plies), 1.5 mm (18 plies) and 2.9 mm (36 plies). Due, probably, to

some inconsistency in the autoclave procedure the latter was slightly below its nominal thickness of 3 mm. The $\pm 45^\circ$ and the $0/90/\pm 45^\circ$ laminates were made only in 1 mm and 1.5 mm thicknesses. The laminates were cut and drilled to provide specimens as described below.

Cutting. The molecular nature of 'Kevlar' fibres, with weak bonding between planes of molecules, results in a tendency to split into fibrils and the low compressive stiffness results in the fibres tending to recede into the matrix, rather than being cut off, during machining. It is, therefore, difficult to achieve a clean edge when cutting KFRP. It has been found (8) that multi-directional laminates are easier to cut than unidirectional and that plain weaves (as here) are better than satin weaves. It has also been shown (9) that the addition of one layer of 120-style glass fabric to the surface, to support the outermost 'Kevlar' plies, improves the quality of the cut edge.

In the current programme three methods of cutting were tried: 1) water jet, 2) diamond impregnated wheel, wet, 3) diamond impregnated wheel, dry (with dust extraction). The second method was eliminated because it was slow and messy. Tensile tests on specimens produced by methods 1) and 3) showed no difference in strength so, although the water jet gave the best finish, method 3) was finally chosen on grounds of speed and convenience.

Drilling. As with cutting, special procedures are necessary to avoid producing holes with fuzzy edges. It was established that vibro-punching produced good quality holes, but was too slow to employ when a large number of holes were required, as here. Following the work of Pinzelli (10) it was found that a modified drill bit also gave good results. This method was not pursued because several bits needed modification and the sharpening procedure was slow and complicated.

The method finally adopted, which gave good quality holes, was to use a conventional drill running at high speed. The laminate, or laminates, were clamped into a metal jig between plates of aluminium alloy. The upper plate was pre-drilled to suit the hole size and acted as a guide. The lower plate was sacrificial. For countersinking a conventional tool had to be used, nothing better being available, although results were not satisfactory.

Fasteners and Specimen Configuration

Riveted Joints. Riveted joints were formed in single cover butt and double cover butt configurations, effectively single lap and double lap respectively, as illustrated in Fig 1. Since the effect of width (w) and end distance (e) were not investigated in this part of the programme these parameters were kept sufficiently large to ensure bearing failure i.e. $w/d > 7$ and $e/d > 5$ (d being the rivet diameter).

The test programme was severely constrained by the availability of rivet types. Hollow Monel ('pop') rivets in three diameters 2.78, 3.18, 4.76 mm (7/64, 1/8, 3/16 inch) were used with a 'dome' head in all diameters but a 100° countersunk head only in 3.18 mm. The 3.18 mm diameter dome head was available in two lengths. In all cases the length corresponded to recommended thicknesses for riveting metal. Solid aluminium rivets were used in only 2.38 (3/32 inch) and 3.18 mm diameters, with a 'mushroom' head for both diameters but a 100° countersunk head, again, only in 3.18 mm. Rivets were trimmed to length (l) according to the relation $l = t + d$, d being rivet diameter and t the total thickness to be joined.

Figure 1 - Configuration of single & double lap riveted joints; definition of dimensions.

The complete set of test configurations for riveted joints can be seen from the results listed in Tables I and II below. The pop rivets were pulled-up by a standard riveting gun, the action of which forms a 'tail' by compressing the length and expanding the diameter of the rivet. Most of this deformation takes place in the region of the tail and an area of damage extending about 0.5 mm radially around the hole in the adjacent laminate was observed in most specimens.

The tail on the solid rivets was formed by hammering down a 'snap'. The rivet head was supported in a suitably shaped 'dolly'. With practice it was possible to always close the rivet using the same number of hammer blows, the action ceasing when the snap just contacted the laminate. The solid rivet is deformed much less than the pop rivet and no damage was observed in any specimen.

Pinned and Bolted Joints. Pins and bolts of only one diameter, 6.35 mm ($\frac{1}{4}$ inch), were used. All specimens were double-ended, of length 200 mm, and either 1.5 or 2.9 mm thick (except for a few pin tests). The load was introduced to the fastener at each end of the specimen via steel links on both sides of the laminate, as shown diagrammatically in Fig 2. For the bolted joints the through-thickness pressure exerted by the nut, when tightened with a standard spanner, was recorded by pre-calibrated load cells equipped with strain gauges. This method gave more consistent results than using just a torque spanner. After drilling as described above holes were finished with a standard reamer. Standard size washers were used with the bolts, inserted between the links and the specimen, as indicated in Fig 2.

Figure 2 - Diagram of bolted joint specimen & method of loading.

Tests and Results

The specimens were loaded in tensile lap-shear in an Instron TT-DM testing machine at a constant rate of 0.2 cm/min. For each test a load-cross-head displacement curve was obtained from the testing machine's plotter. The riveted specimens were mounted directly into the machine's wedge grip jaws - no end plates were affixed to the specimens. Some specimens were sectioned after testing for microscopic examination. For most configurations 3 or 4 replicates were tested.

Failure can occur in four basic modes as illustrated diagrammatically in Fig 3. The cleavage mode can normally be avoided by correct dimensioning of the specimen. Failure load, \hat{P} , was taken to be either the maximum in a test with a continuous load-extension curve, or that at which a sudden drop in the curve first occurred. Failure load was then converted into bearing stress, σ_b , net tensile stress, σ_{TN} , or shear stress, σ_s , defined in the standard way, as follows:

Figure 3 - Basic failure modes of mechanically fastened joints.

$$\sigma_b = \hat{P}/dt \quad (1)$$

$$\sigma_{tn} = \hat{P}/(w-d)t \quad (2)$$

$$\sigma_s = \hat{P}/2et \quad (3)$$

where the dimensions are defined in Fig 1.

The strengths of riveted joints are given in Tables I and II. Irrespective of failure mode strength is quoted as a bearing stress; both mean values and standard deviations are listed. Data for the bolted joints are given in Figs 6 and 8, in which maximum and minimum loads are indicated; the curves are drawn through mean values.

Table I. Bearing Strength of Joints with Pop Rivets

Diam. (mm)	Head	0/90° lay-up						± 45°		0/90/± 45°	
		12-ply		16-ply	18-ply		12-ply		12-ply		
		S/L	D/L	S/L	S/L	D/L	S/L	D/L	S/L	D/L	
2.78 (Type 321)	D	141 (15) _P	270 (11) _B					206 (28) _P		218 (24) _P	
3.18 (Type 419)	D	229 (6) _P									
3.18 (Type 424)	D	229 (12) _P	380 (12) _B	198 (19) _P	255 (14) _P		228 (6) _P	353 (13) _B	252 (12) _P	513 (15) _B	
4.76 (Type 630)	D	367 (7) _P				443 (2) _B	410 (3) _P	659 (12) _B			
3.18 (Type 429)	C				252 (7) _P	416 (12) _B		383 (0) _B		555 (4) _B	
<p><u>Key:</u> Bearing strengths are in MN/m². Mean values listed, standard deviations in brackets. D ≡ dome head, C ≡ countersunk head. S/L ≡ single lap, D/L ≡ double lap.</p> <p>Type number (in Diameter column) relates to rivet length and is reference of the manufacturer, G Tucker, Birmingham, UK.</p> <p>Failure: P ≡ rivet pull-through, B ≡ laminate bearing, * ≡ one rivet head (in four tests).</p>											

Table II. Bearing Strength of Joints with Solid Rivets

Diam. (mm)	Head	0/90° lay-up				± 45°		0/90/± 45°	
		12-ply		18-ply		12-ply		12-ply	
		S/L	D/L	S/L	D/L	S/L	D/L	S/L	D/L
2.38	M		562 (10) _B	308 (13) _S	595 (9) _S	426 (18) _P	622 (26) _B	351 (17) _H	659 (18) _B
3.18	M	364 (32) _P	517 (4) _B	616 (32) _P	826 (66) _B	409 (18) _P	592 (41) _B	366 (36) _P	695 (19) _B
3.18	C				474 (1) _S		505 (10) _B		600 (33) _B

Key: Bearing strengths are in MN/m². Mean values listed, standard deviations in brackets.
M ≡ mushroom head, C ≡ countersunk head.
S/L ≡ single lap, D/L ≡ double lap.

Failure: P ≡ rivet pull-through, S ≡ rivet shear,
H ≡ rivet head, B ≡ laminate bearing.

Discussion of Results for Rivets

Failure Modes

Single Lap Joints. The inherent eccentricity of loading means that a single lap joint bends as soon as load is applied. Continued loading causes the rivet to bend and rotate, as shown in Fig 4, and so apply high local stresses to the outer plies of each laminate on the side of the rivet nearest the load. Thus, only at very low loads will the laminate be loaded uni-

Figure 4 - Rotation of pop rivet in a single lap joint.

formly through the thickness along the contacting face between rivet and hole. Bearing failure of the laminate will not, therefore, occur. Further loading either causes the rivet tail to pull through the laminate or the rivet head to snap off, as observed in the current programme for pop and solid rivets respectively, and indicated in Tables I and II.

Clearly the magnitude of joint bending and rivet rotation will be influenced, for a given laminate thickness, by the stiffness of the rivet and the through-thickness clamping force exerted by the rivet. Rivet stiffness will be determined by rivet type - hollow or solid, diameter and material. Clamping force will be determined by rivet type, head type and head size. For hollow rivets the clamping force will also be dependent on rivet length.

We would, then, expect the failure load to be higher for round head compared to countersunk rivets (greater clamping and rotational restraint), for solid compared to hollow rivets (greater stiffness) and for larger diameters (greater stiffness). In general, this was found to be the case, as seen from Tables I and II (note that a higher bearing stress for a smaller diameter may not mean a higher load), although the discontinuous lengths in which the pop rivets are made tends to complicate matters.

In order to reduce rivet rotation a few single lap specimens were manufactured using the Type 321 pop rivet with washers under the head and tail. There was a 125% increase in strength compared to the basic case ($\sigma_b = 141 \text{ MN/m}^2$, Table I) giving a joint which was stronger than the double lap with the same rivet and the single lap with the Type 424 rivet.

Double Lap Joints. The symmetry of the double lap joint means that there is no overall bending and, hence, rotation of the joint. However, the load in the cover plates is eccentric relative to that in the central plate and so bending of the rivets will occur. Most of the failures observed here were in bearing of the central laminate. This result was surprising since it was expected that the cover plates would provide through-thickness support to the central plate, which would then fail at a higher stress.

For thicker plates the bearing strength of the laminate may exceed the strength of the rivet which will fail either in shear or, for smaller diameters leading to excessive rivet bending, by failure at the head. Such rivet failures occurred only for the solid types and are indicated in Table II.

Joint Type

It is seen from Tables I and II that irrespective of rivet type, head type, diameter or laminate lay-up, a double lap joint is always stronger than a single lap in the same thickness laminate. The relative increase in strength is not the same for all configurations, being largest (> 100%) for the 3.18 mm dome head pop rivet in the $0/90 \pm 45^\circ$ laminate. The strength was nearly doubled for the same laminate with 3.18 mm mushroom head solid rivets and for the $0/90^\circ$ lay-up with 2.78 mm dome head pop rivets and 2.38 mm mushroom head solid rivets. The $\pm 45^\circ$ lay-up showed a smaller increase due, presumably, to the lower laminate bearing strength.

The similarly poor performance of the joints with countersunk pop rivets was also caused by low bearing strength, in this case due to the type of rivet.

Rivet Type

Comparison of rivet types can be made by considering the data for 3.18 mm rivets - pop, with dome and countersunk heads; solid, with mushroom and countersunk heads.

It is seen that for the same lay-up, thickness and joint type, solid rivets always give a stronger joint. Strict comparison is not possible since the mushroom head of the solid rivet is larger than the dome head of the pop rivet, thus conferring greater resistance to rivet rotation and, presumably, greater clamping force. However, it should be noted that the strength increase is relatively less for the countersunk head rivets, confirming that this head type is less effective than a rounded head. The other complicating factor is whether the length of the pop rivet is correct; this will be discussed later.

Rivet Head Geometry

As previously stated it was expected that a round head (dome or mushroom) would, compared to a countersunk head, confer a greater resistance to rivet rotation, impose a higher through-thickness clamping force and offer more support to the surface layers, thus inhibiting failure in a 'brush-like' manner. In addition, a countersunk head will transfer relatively little in bearing thus giving a higher average stress over the smaller shank length. We would, therefore, expect joints with countersunk heads to be weaker. This reduced strength is indeed seen with the solid rivets (only double laps compared) which were trimmed to length to suit the total thickness being riveted. However, with the pop rivets either no difference was seen or the joints with countersunk rivets were slightly stronger than those with dome head rivets.

It is the single lap joint in the 18-ply 0/90° laminate that shows similar strength for dome and countersunk pop rivets (3.18 mm). Behaviour in this instance is dominated by joint bending and rivet rotation and failure will be limited by the pull-through strength of the laminate. The head type is, therefore, relatively unimportant. For the same diameter pop rivets, double lap joints in 12-ply $\pm 45^\circ$ and 0/90/ $\pm 45^\circ$ laminates showed a strength increase with countersunk compared to dome heads. According to the manufacturers the Type 424 rivet is recommended for joining total thicknesses between 1.8 and 3.05 mm and the Type 429 for thicknesses between 3.07 and 4.32 mm. The joints under consideration were 3 mm thick and thus the Type 424 appears suitable. However, only the dome head was available in this length, the countersunk head being available only in the larger size. The results indicate that pulling-up the longer rivet resulted in a larger through-thickness clamping force which more than offset the detrimental effect of the countersunk head. The recommended thicknesses are based on metal practice and clearly different standards are likely to apply to composites.

Rivet Diameter and Laminate Thickness

For the single lap joints which failed mainly by rivet pull-through, strength increased with rivet diameter. This is to be expected since the rotational resistance of the rivet is closely related to stiffness and, therefore, diameter.

For the double lap joints that failed in bearing the trends are confusing and evidence very limited. It is seen from the data for 0/90° lay-ups with solid rivets that strength increases with laminate thickness, for a

constant diameter; i.e. with decreasing d/t . This is explained by the greater resistance to local buckling of the surface plies, on the loaded side of the hole, of the thicker plate. We would then expect, for a consistent trend with d/t , strength to increase with decreasing diameter for a constant thickness. This is seen to be so with solid rivets for 12-ply 0/90° and ± 45° lay-ups, but not for the 0/90/± 45° lay-ups. Neither is it so for pop-riveted joints, although here trends are influenced by the variation in clamping force and the differing effect of this on each lay-up.

Laminate Lay-up

Work on bolted joints in CFRP and GFRP laminates manufactured from unidirectional prepreg, (2) and (3), has shown that a mixture of 0° fibres, to sustain the compressive (bearing) load from the fastener, and ± 45° fibres, to constrain the 0° layers against lateral splitting, gives optimum bearing performance. The woven material used in this project meant that such a lay-up could not be investigated. However, the nearest equivalent, the 0/90/± 45° lay-up, did give the highest bearing strength (see 12-ply laminates, Type 424 rivet in Table I and both mushroom head rivets in Table II; double lap joints).

With the pop rivets the 0/90° lay-up is stronger than the ± 45°, whereas the reverse is true for joints with solid rivets. It is felt that this is related to the greater clamping force exerted by the solid rivets, and shows that the ± 45° lay-up, which is inherently weak in compression, possesses an acceptable bearing strength when adequately restrained. Certainly continued loading of the joints produces different failure behaviour, as illustrated in Fig 5 which shows the central plate from double lap joints. Compared to the pop-riveted joints, Figs 5 (a) and (b), the solid riveted joints, Figs 5 (d) and (e), change from a progressive mode, extending the initial failure, to a catastrophic tensile mode. This failure behaviour is also seen with bolted joints and will be discussed again below. The 0/90/± 45° lay-up, Figs 5 (c) and (f), behaves in the same way, deforming into folds ahead of the rivet, for both rivet types.

Other Composite Materials

Data on riveted joints in other composites is limited, some general data being presented by Godwin et al (4). More detail on single lap CFRP joints, in laminates of unidirectional prepreg, is given by Matthews et al (11). In the latter work several of the factors discussed above are also examined, the general trends being the same as here. The strength of the CFRP joints was overall better, being between 25 and 83% higher than for equivalent KFRP configurations.

Figure 5 - Central plate from failed riveted double lap joints; 3.18 mm rivet. $0/90^\circ$, $\pm 45^\circ$, $0/90^\circ/\pm 45^\circ$ lay-ups respectively in a), b) & c) for pop rivets and in d), e) & f) for solid rivets.

Discussion of Results for Pins and Bolts

With the riveted joints dimensions were chosen in order to induce bearing failure. With the bolted and pinned joints a wider view was taken and joint geometry was altered to give tension and shear out, as well as bearing failure. The through-thickness clamping force, unquantified with the riveted joints, was also closely monitored. Diameter was constant throughout at 6.35 mm. A few preliminary tests on tensile specimens containing a hole showed minimal change in net tensile strength as specimen width was reduced. This notch insensitivity was also noted by van Dreumel (6).

Pinned Joints

Effect of Width (w). When width was varied at a constant large end distance, for 18-ply laminates, over the range $2d$ to $7d$ virtually no change in strength was found except for $\pm 45^\circ$ laminates which showed a decrease for widths below $3.5d$. At large values of width the bearing strength order was: $0/90^\circ/\pm 45^\circ$ (165 MN/m^2), $0/90^\circ$ (150 MN/m^2), $\pm 45^\circ$ (120 MN/m^2). Even with widths as low as $2d$ bearing failure occurred for $0/90^\circ$ and $0/90^\circ/\pm 45^\circ$ lay-ups. Very narrow $\pm 45^\circ$ lay-ups failed in tension with the drop in strength mentioned above.

Effect of End Distance (e). Repeating the previous set of tests, but varying end distance instead of width, gave similar results. The same bearing stresses as previously were obtained, showing virtually no change with end distance. Even with $e = 2d$ failure for all lay-ups was still in bearing. For smaller end distances continued loading caused inter-ply delaminations leading ultimately to cleavage failure.

Through-thickness Clamping

With pinned joints the absence of any through-thickness restraint means that the laminate will fail, at low loads, in a 'brush-like' manner on the loaded side of the pin. This is because the through-thickness tensile stress, induced by the compressive bearing stress, causes inter-ply delaminations.

With a bolted joint the presence of the washers under the nut and bolt head prevent the above failure mode occurring, even if the nut is only 'finger-tight', with a consequent increase in failure load. In the current tests the increase was found to be (compared to the pinned case) 180% (i.e. 2.80 times) for $0/90 \pm 45^\circ$, 120% for $0/90^\circ$ and 130% for $\pm 45^\circ$ laminates.

As the nut was tightened the following further increases in bearing strength were seen at a through-thickness pressure (bolt tensile force \div washer area) of 15 MN/m^2 : - $0/90 \pm 45^\circ$, 26%; $0/90^\circ$, 39%; $\pm 45^\circ$ lay-up, 53%. Above 15 MN/m^2 no additional increase in strength was observed. Similar increases in strength are also seen with unidirectional prepreg constructions of CFRP (2) and GFRP (3). However, the increases between pinned and finger-tight conditions are much higher for the KFRP laminates tested here. This is thought to be due to the inherently low value of compressive strength of 'Kevlar' fibre and thus the presence of through-thickness constraint, which inhibits micro-buckling and fibre degradation into fibrils, assumes a much greater importance. All subsequent tests were conducted with a clamping pressure of 17 MN/m^2 , a value chosen to ensure full clamping.

Bolted Joints; Effect of Width

The general behaviour, as illustrated in Fig 6, is similar to that for CFRP and GFRP, (2) and (3). Strength increases, eventually becoming constant at a value of width which depends on lay-up. The width values for maximum (i.e. bearing) strength of $0/90^\circ$ and $\pm 45^\circ$ lay-ups compare well with those found by Collings (2) for CFRP. The $0/90^\circ$ lay-up is least sensitive to width changes. This behaviour should be compared to the pin-joints which were, effectively, insensitive to width change.

The strength hierarchy of lay-ups is seen to be the same as for pinned joints ($0/90 \pm 45^\circ$; $0/90^\circ$; $\pm 45^\circ$), the reversal of position of the $0/90^\circ$ and $\pm 45^\circ$ lay-ups that might have been expected, based on the pop and solid rivet tests (for the latter $\pm 45^\circ$ is stronger than $0/90^\circ$), was not seen between the pinned and bolted results. The general level of bearing stress is seen to be less than for GFRP which, in turn, is weaker than CFRP (3) ($700 - 900$ and $850 - 1100 \text{ MN/m}^2$ respectively).

Figure 6 - Variation of bolted joint strength with w/d ; 1.5 mm laminates.

Although for smaller widths (initial linear portion of curves in Fig 6) failure was in a tensile mode, even at high values of w/d tensile cracks occurred at the hole edge, following bearing failure, leading ultimately to tensile failure if loading continued. This was seen for all lay-ups although the position of the initial cracks and the direction of propagation depended on lay-up. The $0/90/\pm 45^\circ$ lay-up was the most resistant to crack propagation. This failure behaviour was quite different to that of the pinned joints and is clearly associated with the through-thickness restraint and clamping force. The change in stress distribution around the hole as described by Matthews et al (12), whilst preventing the brush-like failure mode, makes it easier for failure to occur in another mode. The failure of a $0/90^\circ$ lay-up is shown in Fig 7 for both pinned and bolted joints. Note that the pin test was one of the few carried out on 1 mm thick laminates. The same behaviour was seen for thicker specimens.

It was also noticed that the wide thinner laminates (1.5 mm) showed gross bending on the loaded side of the bolt at high values of w/d . This produced local damage to surface layers at the hole edge in a similar manner to that caused by rivet rotation. The thicker (2.9 mm) laminates did not bend in this manner and $0/90^\circ$ laminates showed a consequent 8% increase in strength.

(a)

(b)

Figure 7 - Failure of 0/90° laminates; a) pinned, 1 mm thick, b) bolted, 1.5 mm thick.

Bolted Joints; Effect of End Distance

The effect of changing end distance was investigated only for the 0/90° lay-up. The results, which are similar to those seen for CFRP (2) and GFRP (3), are shown in Fig 8 and again strength becomes constant at high values of end distance.

Figure 8 - Variation of bolted joint strength with e/d ; 1.5 mm laminates.

For $e/d > 3.5$ failure occurred initially in bearing, although cracks propagating from the hole edge (at 90° to the load direction) caused ultimate failure in tension. For $e/d = 1.5$ failure was in a cleavage mode. For values of e/d between 1.5 and 3.5 failure was tensile and is thus quite different to CFRP and GFRP, with this geometry, which show a shear out mode. The difference in behaviour is associated with the woven fabric, which is used here, being more resistant to shear out failure than are unidirectional prepreg laminates.

Bolted Joints; Effect of Laminate Thickness

It was mentioned above that strength increased with thickness, although this effect was only investigated here for 0/90° laminates in 1.5 and 2.9 mm thicknesses. When plotted against increasing d/t the reduction was slower than results obtained from the tests on pinned joints. This agrees with data on CFRP (2) and GFRP (3) joints. The same behaviour was seen in the

current work with double lap joints in the same lay-up with solid rivets.

Bolted Joints; Effect of Lay-up

The $\pm 45^\circ$ lay-up gave the lowest bearing strength (see Fig 6). After initial bearing failure cracks, which initiate at $\pm 45^\circ$ to the load direction, propagate at $\pm 45^\circ$ towards the specimen edge. The $0/90^\circ$ lay-up was stronger than the $\pm 45^\circ$ lay-up. In this case initial bearing failure was followed by ultimate tensile failure due to cracks initiating at $\pm 90^\circ$ to the load direction and propagating across the net section. These results are different to those found for CFRP and GFRP (3) for which $\pm 45^\circ$ is stronger in bearing than $0/90^\circ$. As mentioned above, when discussing solid rivets, $\pm 45^\circ$ lay-ups, although possessing low compressive strength, show enhanced bearing behaviour when adequately restrained. Clearly with the KFRP the very complex interaction between the stress field and the poor compressive properties of 'Kevlar' fibre prevent restrained $\pm 45^\circ$ being stronger than $0/90^\circ$ lay-ups.

It might have been expected that the $0/90/\pm 45^\circ$ lay-up would have a strength between the others. In fact, this combination of $\pm 45^\circ$ fibres, with low bearing strength, high shear stiffness and low stress concentration factor (SCF) and $0/90^\circ$ fibres, with higher bearing strength and SCF, proved to be the strongest. It is known from work on unidirectional prepreg laminates that the presence of $\pm 45^\circ$ fibres enhances the bearing performance of 0° fibres (13).

Tensile Strength

The tensile strength can be examined by considering the variation of net tensile stress (Equation (2)) with width. For both pins and bolts, for all lay-ups, this stress (although not the failure load) decreases as width increases. The $\pm 45^\circ$ lay-up was least sensitive. These results agree broadly with those found by Collings (2) for CFRP.

Shear Strength

Using Equation (3) it is possible to examine the variation of shear strength. This is found to decrease with increasing end distance for pins in all lay-ups and bolts in $0/90^\circ$ lay-up (others not tested). In contrast to the work of Collings (2) who showed that $\pm 45^\circ$ were better than $0/90^\circ$ lay-ups, the opposite was seen here. This may have been due to the characteristics of the woven fabric as compared to unidirectional prepreg material.

Comparison with Other Composites

As mentioned above considerable data exists for laminates made from unidirectional prepreg and comparisons have been drawn where appropriate. In the current programme tests were also conducted on riveted joints in woven CFRP. However, quantitative comparison was not possible due to differences in ply thickness (0.257 cf. 0.083 mm), weave (five shaft satin cf. plain) and matrix (Ciba-Geigy 914 cf. 913 resin) of the available materials.

The carbon fibre joints were found to be stronger but the important difference was in the 'brittle' behaviour of the CFRP and the 'ductile' behaviour of the KFRP. With the CFRP joints initial failure was followed almost immediately by ultimate failure, the laminate around the rivet breaking into many small fragments, whereas the KFRP material sustained load to quite large joint displacements after initial failure, the laminate

in this case deforming into folds on the loaded side of the rivet.

There are also considerable differences in the micro-mechanisms of failure, as shown in Fig 9. The CFRP fails by a combination of fibre cracking, matrix cracking and delamination. The KFRP, in contrast, fails by gross deformation of layers with little, if any, fibre or matrix cracking; delamination occurs only after prolonged loading.

(a)

(b)

Figure 9 - Micrographs on failed specimens; (a) CFRP, (b) KFRP.

Conclusions

For mechanically fastened joints in the woven 'Kevlar' fibre fabric with Ciba-Geigy 913 resin tested here, the following conclusions may be drawn:

General

1. Damage caused by cutting, drilling or riveting causes an insignificant loss in strength.
2. The load-deflection behaviour is essentially ductile.
3. A $0/90 \pm 45^\circ$ lay-up is stronger than a $0/90^\circ$ which is stronger than a $\pm 45^\circ$ lay-up.

Riveted Joints

1. Double lap are always stronger than single lap joints.
2. In general, failure load is higher with solid than hollow rivets and with round head than countersunk heads.
3. For single lap joints strength increases with rivet diameter.
4. In general, strength increases with decreasing d/t for double lap joints with solid rivts.
5. Recommended rivet lengths based on metals practice may not be optimum for composites.

Pinned Joints

1. Strength is virtually insensitive to changes in width and end distance.
2. Bearing failure occurs even at very low values of w/d and e/d .
3. Thicker laminates are stronger than thin laminates.

Bolted Joints

1. Finger-tight bolts produce a significant strength increase compared to pinned joints. Strength increases further as the bolt nut is tightened.
2. Through-thickness clamping changes the failure mode, compared to pinned joints. Ultimate failure is always tensile, even for large values of w/d and e/d .
3. Strength increases to a constant value at high values of w/d and e/d .
4. Strength increases with laminate thickness.

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